

The project aimed to develop and validate a state-of-the-art Industry-Academia Collaboration mechanism for quick, challenge-driven, human-centred co-creation.

The EU-funded **INDUSAC** project has successfully developed and tested a new, human-centred, challenge-driven co-creation mechanism that connects industry with academia across Europe. Over three years of implementation, the project supported international teams of students and researchers in tackling innovation needs directly submitted by companies.

270+

companies

450+

students

130+

researchers

The **INDUSAC** project created a dynamic community of industry-academia stakeholders focused on circularity, general sustainability, digitalisation and industry 4.0.

Using a dedicated digital platform and a structured methodology, **INDUSAC** facilitated fast, cost-effective, and inclusive **collaborations between over 250 companies and academic teams.**

The project featured an open call for both companies and academic teams - open from October 2023 (for companies) and November 2023 (for students and researchers) - with multiple cut-off dates allowing companies to submit challenges (15 Dec. 2023, 15 Apr. 2024, 15 Nov. 2024, 15 Mar. 2025) and academic teams to submit motivation letters across several rounds (11 Feb. 2024; 18 Jun. 2024; 30 Sep. 2024; 30 Oct. 2024; 30 Nov. 2024; and early 2025 cut-offs: 30 Jan.; 28 Feb.; 31 Mar.; 15 Apr. 2025).

Strong Results and Wide Engagement

- A total of **251 industry challenges** were published via the INDUSAC platform.
- **232** motivation letters.
- More than **190 students received financial support** of up to €1,000 each for their participation.
- **67%** of participants came from EU “widening countries,” helping to create a more balanced and inclusive innovation landscape.
- **163** completed co-creation projects.
- Over **584 students and researchers** engaged in real business environments.
- **159 solutions** accepted by companies.
- Average **satisfaction scores** exceeded 4.2 out of 5 for both the process and the platform.
- **90%** of students and researchers reported an **improvement** in transversal and entrepreneurial skills.
- **Over 91%** of participants would **recommend INDUSAC** to their peers.

Final Event in Vienna

The project concluded with its **final event**, which took place on **8–9 May 2025 in Vienna, Austria**, as part of the **EIT Manufacturing Day**. The meeting brought together **over 500 participants**, including representatives of companies, students, researchers, and policymakers.

During the event, the consortium presented the **results achieved throughout the project**, demonstrated the functionalities of the **INDUSAC platform**, and conducted interactive workshops focused on the future development of the co-creation mechanism. Panel discussions addressed the role of industry-academia collaboration in driving innovation and skills development.

Further details and a full photo gallery are available on the project website: [INDUSAC – Two intense days in Vienna to wrap up the project.](#)

